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Makhliyo NasirovaNational Research University
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and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers”**Bakhtiyor Pulatov**Research Institute of Environment
and Nature Conservation Technologies**ANALYSIS OF THE OBSERVED AND SIMULATED WHEAT YIELD DATA UNDER
CLIMATE CHANGE IN TASHKENT REGION** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8264233>**ABSTRACT**

Tashkent region in Uzbekistan is an area that is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. This area is already one of the most arid and water-scarce regions in the world. Climate change is predicted to exacerbate these challenges, particularly through increasing temperatures, decreasing rainfall, and more frequent extreme weather events. AquaCrop is an efficient tool that has been used to simulate various crops, including wheat, under different environmental conditions. The model considers crop physiology and water use efficiency, allowing it to predict crop yield under different water and temperature regimes. In this research AquaCrop crop model was tested in Bekabad district of Tashkent region. The model was calibrated based on the collected secondary agricultural data and climate indicators. Wheat yield indicators for 1998-2016 were compared based on observed data and simulation results. AquaCrop crop model predicted the wheat yield obtained in 1998-2016 in Bekobad with an error of 4.69 c/ha. In this case, the absolute error of the average indicator is 9 c/ha, the average squared error is 0.7 c/ha and the Pearson correlation is 0.65c/ha.

Keywords: Bekabad, AquaCrop, wheat, climate change, yield prediction, Tashkent region

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HOSILDORLIGINING KUZATILGAN VA MODELLASHTIRILGAN
MA'LUMOTLARINI TAHLIL QILISH**

ANNOTATSIYA

O'zbekistonning Toshkent viloyati iqlim o'zgarishi ta'siriga sezuvchan hudud hisoblanadi. Bu hudud dunyodagi eng qurg'oqchil va suv tanqis hududlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Iqlim o'zgarishi, ayniqsa, haroratning oshishi, yog'ingarchilikning kamayishi va tez-tez sodir bo'ladigan ekstremal ob-havo hodisalari tufayli bu muammolarni yanada kuchaytiradi. AquaCrop turli xil ekinlarni, shu jumladan bug'doyni turli xil ekologik sharoitlarda modellashtirish uchun ishlatiladigan samarali vositadir. Model ekinlarning fiziologiyasi va suvdan foydalanish samaradorligini inobatga oladi, bu unga turli xil suv va harorat rejimlarida hosilni bashorat qilish imkonini beradi. Ushbu tadqiqotda AquaCrop ekin modeli Toshkent viloyatining Bekobod tumanida sinovdan o'tkazildi. Model yig'ilgan ikkilamchi qishloq xo'jaligi ma'lumotlari va iqlim ko'rsatkichlari asosida kalibratsiya qilingan. 1998-2016 yillardagi bug'doy hosildorligi ko'rsatkichlari statistik ma'lumotlar va model natijalari bilan taqqoslandi. AquaCrop ekin modeli 1998-2016 yillarda Bekobodda olingan bug'doy hosilini 4,69 ts/ga xato bilan bashorat qilish imkonini berdi. Bunda o'rtacha indikatorning mutlaq xatosi 9 s/ga, o'rtacha kvadrat xatosi 0,7 s/ga va Pearson korrelyatsiyasi 0,65 s/ga ni tashkil qildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bekobod, AquaCrop, bug'doy, iqlim o'zgarishi, hosilni bashorat qilish, Toshkent viloyati

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**АНАЛИЗ НАБЛЮДАЕМЫХ И СМОДЕЛИРОВАННЫХ ДАННЫХ ОБ
УРОЖАЙНОСТИ ПШЕНИЦЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ КЛИМАТА В
ТАШКЕНТСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ташкентская область в Узбекистане является территорией, которая особенно уязвима к последствиям изменения климата. Этот район уже является одним из самых засушливых и маловодных регионов мира. Прогнозируется, что изменение климата усугубит эти проблемы, особенно из-за повышения температуры, уменьшения количества осадков и более частых экстремальных погодных явлений. AquaCrop — это эффективный инструмент, который использовался для моделирования различных культур, включая пшеницу, в различных условиях окружающей среды. Модель учитывает физиологию растений и эффективность использования воды, что позволяет прогнозировать урожайность при различных режимах воды и температуры. В данном исследовании культурная модель AquaCrop была испытана в Бекабадском районе Ташкентской области. Модель была откалибрована на основе собранных вторичных сельскохозяйственных данных и климатических показателей. Показатели урожайности пшеницы за 1998-2016 гг. сравнивались на основе данных наблюдений и результатов моделирования. Модель урожая AquaCrop предсказала урожайность пшеницы, полученную в 1998-2016 гг. в Бекобаде, с ошибкой 4,69 ц/га. При этом абсолютная ошибка среднего показателя составляет 9 ц/га, среднеквадратическая ошибка 0,7 ц/га и корреляция Пирсона 0,65 ц/га.

Ключевые слова: Бекабад, AquaCrop, пшеница, изменение климата, прогноз урожайности, Ташкентская область

Introduction

Tashkent region in Uzbekistan is an area that is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. This region is located in Central Asia, which is already one of the most arid and water-scarce regions in the world. Climate change is predicted to exacerbate these challenges,

particularly through increasing temperatures, decreasing rainfall, and more frequent extreme weather events (Babakholov et al. 2022).

Tashkent Region is home to approximately 4.4 million people and has a largely agricultural-based economy. The region is known for its production of wheat, cotton, and fruit trees, which are all vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. Crop yields are already declining due to increasing temperatures and decreasing rainfall, and this trend is expected to worsen in the future (Nasirova, Pulatov, and Pulatov 2023).

Moreover, climate change is expected to increase the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, including droughts (Khasanov et al. 2023) and floods. These events can cause severe damage to infrastructure, homes, and crops, leading to significant economic losses (Ahn and Juraev 2023).

It is predicted that world trade in grains will grow by 15% and reach 531 million tons by 2031. Wheat will account for about 40% of this growth, while corn, rice and other coarse grains will account for 30%, 16% and 8%, respectively (OECD/FAO 2022). However, wheat production is significantly influenced by climate variability, particularly rainfall and temperature changes, which can cause yield losses and reduce crop quality (Zhong, Zhou, and Jiang 2022). Climate change is predicted to worsen these impacts, particularly in regions already vulnerable to extreme weather events (Mirza and Mirza 2003), such as the Tashkent region in Uzbekistan.

The Tashkent region is a significant wheat-producing area, but it is also susceptible to frequent droughts and high temperatures, which can significantly reduce yields. Accurate yield prediction is essential for improving wheat production and managing the impacts of climate change on agricultural systems. Crop models such as AquaCrop have emerged as powerful tools to simulate crop growth and yield under different environmental conditions.

AquaCrop is a widely used model that simulates crop growth and yield under limited water supply conditions (Zarei and Moghimi 2019; Rashid et al. 2019; Nouri et al. 2019). It has been used to simulate various crops, including wheat, under different environmental conditions. The model considers crop physiology and water use efficiency, allowing it to predict crop yield under different water and temperature regimes (Han et al. 2019; Rashid et al. 2019).

This study aims to apply the AquaCrop model to predict wheat yields under climate change. The study will provide critical insights into the impact of climate change on wheat production in the Tashkent region, allowing for the development of effective adaptation strategies to manage the effects of climate change on agriculture.

The objective of this study is to address an essential issue in global agriculture by predicting wheat yields under varying environmental conditions in the Tashkent region. The study's results are expected to contribute to a better understanding of the impacts of climate change on wheat production and support the development of strategies to sustainably manage and improve wheat production in the region.

Methods and Materials

The study area is Bekabad district which is located in the south of the Tashkent region (Fig.1). It has an area of 760 km² and it had more than 162 thousand inhabitants. The urban population is almost 29 thousand people, the rural population is nearly 133 thousand people. The territory of the district is located in the Dalvarzin desert and partly in Mirzachol. The climate is strictly continental. The average temperature in January is -2.5°, in July it is 28.5°. Annual rainfall is 227 mm. The vegetation period is 220 days. There will be a lot of wind (at a speed of 15 m/sec during 102 days) in the south of the district. Sometimes, the wind speed reaches 30-45 m/sec. The Syr Darya flows from the southeast to the northeast. There are residual lakes (Qalgansir, Katta Kurgansir, Yangikol, Haibatkol, Kazan, Shorkol) on the coast of Syrdarya. Dalvarzin (with right and left branches), Jivali, Ortogli, Dostlik canals and Khasyoz stream flow through. The soil is meadow and meadow-swamp, draining gray soil. The main crops are wheat, rice and cotton.

Figure 1. Geographical location of the study area

The research attempted to use AquaCrop crop growth simulation model which is developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). It is designed to assess the impact of water and environmental stresses on crop growth and yield (Fig.2). AquaCrop is widely used to optimize water management strategies and improve water use efficiency in agriculture, especially in areas facing water scarcity and drought conditions.

Figure 2. Calculation scheme of AquaCrop with an indication (dotted arrows) of the processes affected by water stress (a to e) and temperature stress (f to g). CC is the simulated canopy cover, CCpot the potential canopy cover, Zr the rooting depth, ETo the reference evapotranspiration, GDD the growing degree days, WP* the normalized crop water productivity, and HI the Harvest Index.

AquaCrop supports a range of crop types, including cereals, root crops, fruits, vegetables, and various grasses. Users need to select the specific crop they want to simulate. For each selected crop, AquaCrop requires certain parameters that define its growth characteristics, such as the potential crop growth rate, water stress thresholds, and crop-specific coefficients that describe water and

temperature responses. Information about the soil type, depth, and hydraulic properties are essential inputs for AquaCrop (Fig.3).

Soil data plays a significant role in determining water availability to the crop and the root zone depth. AquaCrop uses climate data, such as daily weather information (temperature, solar radiation, wind speed) and precipitation, to calculate potential evapotranspiration (ET₀) and crop water requirements (Fig.4).

Figure 3. Input data defining the environment in which the crop develops

Mean air temperature

Mean monthly Rainfall and ET₀

Reference evapotranspiration

Figure 4. Climate data of the study area

The model allows users to specify different irrigation strategies, including the frequency, timing, and amount of water applied during the growing season. AquaCrop operates on a daily time step and simulates the growth of the crop throughout the growing season. It calculates crop water requirements based on ET₀, crop coefficients, and stress factors due to water deficit, and then estimates crop growth and yield.

AquaCrop considers the effects of water stress and heat stress on crop growth. It applies stress factors to the crop growth rate and biomass production, depending on the available soil water content and the crop's specific response to stress. The model provides various output parameters, such as crop yield, crop biomass, water productivity, and other indicators of crop performance under specific environmental and management conditions.

The study is conducted based on secondary crop and climate data. Wheat yield data between 1998-2016 is used from The State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics (UZSTAT).

Daily maximum and minimum temperature, precipitation and wind speed data from 1997 to 2016 provided by the meteorological station “Bekabad” of the Centre of Hydrometeorological Service under the Cabinet of Ministries of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Uzhydromet).

Results

In this research AquaCrop crop model was tested in Bekabad district of Tashkent region. In this, wheat yield indicators for 2005-2015 were compared based on statistical data and model results. The model was calibrated based on the collected secondary agricultural data and climate indicators (Fig.5).

Figure 5. Simulation results and observed wheat yield (centner/hectare) between 1998-2016

According to the obtained results, AquaCrop crop model predicted the wheat yield obtained in 1998-2016 in Bekabad district of Tashkent region with an error of 4.69 c/ha. In this case, the absolute error of the average indicator is 9 c/ha, the average squared error is 0.7 c/ha and the Pearson correlation is 0.65c/ha.

Conclusion

The following findings are drawn from this study, which examines the accuracy of AquaCrop model in Bekabad district: AquaCrop crop model predicted the wheat yield obtained in Bekabad between 1998-2016 with RMSE of 0.7 c/ha. Taking into account that this study is based only on secondary crop and climate data it is suggested application of field data may improve the accuracy of model simulation results.

Statistical indicators (unit)	
Mean Absolute Error, (c/ha)	9
Root Mean Square Error, (c/ha)	0,7
Observed, (c/ha)	66,9
Simulated, (c/ha)	62,21
R	0,65

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